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Reflections on the Hipparcos Catalogue

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1. General remarks

I assume that the final Hipparcos catalogue will be published both in machine-readable form (on one or more media, e.g., magnetic tape and CD-ROM) and in printed form. The machine-readable catalogue may contain more data than the printed version — there are obviously items which are impractical to print or of little value for the occasional user (e.g., photometry at individual epochs for variable stars, correlations between parallax and proper motion). On the other hand, whenever an item appears in both versions, I would insist that the data are strictly the same. There should be no ambiguity as to what constitutes the 'official' Hipparcos value! In practice this implies that the same units are used, with the same number of decimal places. According to this principle we should not accept, for instance, to use radians in the machine-readable version, if sexagesimal units are used in the printed.

The information should be limited to the following categories, which really constitute the minimum data set for what we might call a complete catalogue:

1. Data for identification
2. Data derived from the mission
3. Other data which are implicit in the reductions

Identification data includes the HIC number (or rather its equivalent, HOC?) and possibly cross-references to other major catalogues. I assume that this information could be copied from SP-1136 if desirable. However, there may be a case for not giving any cross-references at all. First, as they are already given in SP-1134 there may be little point in reproducing them a second time. Secondly, the identifications in the Input Catalogue defines the targets that were intended for observation. How do we know that the output catalogue really refers to the same objects? I think this is quite difficult and possibly the best solution is to regard the HOC numbers as a separate identifier, with HIC = HOC merely implied as a tentative (although very probable!) identification. The approximate position may serve as an additional identifier (see Section 3 below).

Data implicitly used in the reductions, but not derived from the mission, may include ground-based colours and radial velocities (important for a handful of nearby stars). It is not clear how these data should be given in the catalogue. Colours, for instance, may be given for all the stars with a remark telling if it was derived from the mission (starmappers) or from another source. The RV could be given in a separate table with just a flag in the main catalogue indicating the stars for which secular acceleration was taken into account in the reductions.

The third category of data also includes several 'constants' such as the astronomical unit, GS and GE, as well as the Earth ephemeris used to compute stellar aberration. The values and/or sources of these data must be clearly indicated in an Introduction (or Appendix) to the catalogue.

The catalogue will consist of a main catalogue with one entry per star (or system) and supplementary catalogues for double/multiple stars, variable stars and objects in the solar system. The special and very difficult issue of double and multiple stars is addressed in separate note by Söderhjelm (NDAC/LO/143).

2. Reference frame, epochs etc

The reference frame must be as close as possible to the extragalactic equatorial J2000 frame. The practical realisation of this link is a separate problem, which I will not discuss here.

The positions should be referred to a common epoch for the whole catalogue, close to the actual mean epoch of observation but rounded to some convenient value such as J1991.5. From a user's point of view this is definitely better than having a different epoch for each object (which is really necessary only in pure positional catalogues, i.e., without proper motions). There are two consequences of this: first, the accuracy of the given position is slightly inferior to the best position (corresponding to the mean epoch of observation). Secondly, the errors in position and proper motion are in general correlated. Normally these are matters which only concern the specialist user. Nevertheless, it is possible and in fact quite practicable to retain the full information by the addition of one single data item for each star: the actual mean epoch of observation (assumed to be the same in all directions). The standard errors in position must then refer to that epoch rather than to the common catalogue epoch. This allows to compute the positional errors as a function of epoch, and the data may be combined rigorously with other catalogues, e.g., for the improvement of proper motions.

There is obviously some risk of confusion in that the positional errors do not refer to the stated position (at the common epoch). Indeed, it will be an challenging task for the authors of the Introduction to explain this to the user. However I believe that this inconvenience is more than compensated by the conceptual advantage of having a single catalogue epoch for the positions.

3. Sexagesimal or not?

Most colleagues with which I have discussed this question seem to agree that it is desirable to do something about the old Babylonian heritage, and that the Hipparcos Catalogue would be an ideal occasion to set a new standard. This is indeed my own, very strong feeling. However, it is not so easy in practice. One can either be completely radical, with the obvious risk that it will merely go to history as an interesting anomaly, or take a more cautious approach and eliminate the worst aspects of the sexagesimal system while retaining some of the baggage (like the arcsec). Personally I would favour the more cautious approach. My proposal is therefore:

1. The position (α , δ) is given in (nonagesimal) degrees with a decimal fraction. For easier reading the decimals may be grouped (in three?) in the printed catalogue. This will conform with the way galactic coordinates are usually given, and is immediately appreciated by anyone with a pocket calculator.
2. The parallax is given in mas. This is clearly a case when a link to the old arcsec is desirable. Using mas rather than arcsec should not be controversial (I hope); the mas seems to be well established by now.
3. The proper motions are given in mas/yr (on a great circle, i.e., including the $\cos \delta$ factor).
4. The standard errors on all three items are given in mas and mas/yr, respectively (again on a great circle for α and μ_α).

Not giving the positional standard errors in the same unit as the position itself may seem odd, but, on the other hand, as explained earlier, the standard error does not really apply to that position anyway. The reader should perhaps be forced to regard the standard errors as a separate piece of information (together with the epoch of observation), rather than as something conventionally appended to the measured quantity, as in $x = 1.2345 \pm 0.0012$.

This can be emphasized in the layout of the printed catalogue by not giving the positional errors next to the position.

A somewhat similar argument applies to the proper motion. We should recognize that proper motion data are used for two completely different purposes. One is to transform a position from one epoch to another. The other is as a piece of kinematical information: combined with the parallax it gives the tangential space velocity. For the second purpose it is natural to use mas/yr on a great circle (this allows simple computation e.g. of the total proper motion and its position angle). For propagating a position from one epoch to another it would be more natural to give $d\alpha/dt$ (on a small circle) and $d\delta/dt$ in the same angular unit as α and δ . However, that would in a sense implicate the linear propagation formula $\alpha(T) = \alpha(T_0) + (T - T_0)d\alpha/dt$, etc, the use of which should not be encouraged. For rigorous propagation (either with constant μ along a great circle or with constant space velocity) one needs the kinematical information rather than the derivatives of α , δ ; see Eq. [9.3] in SP-1111, Vol. III).

Finally it is necessary to recognize another consequence of abandoning the sexagesimal position. It will undoubtedly obstruct manual cross-identification based on position only, given that sexagesimal units are used in almost any other catalogue. My solution to that problem would be to give, as an additional *identifier*, the approximate position (to the nearest arcsec and 0.1 sec of time) in the old units. Perhaps this should be expressed in the B1950 frame (and epoch) and one could even give the 50-year differences (precession plus proper motion) for easy conversion to 1900 and 2000.

4. Summary

In summary the printed version of the main catalogue could contain the following items (not necessarily in this order):

- HOC number and an approximate position (sexagesimal) for identification;
- the position (α , δ in deg) at the catalogue epoch;
- the actual mean epoch of observation and the positional errors at that epoch (in mas);
- the magnitude (H_p) and colour ($B_T - V_T$) with standard errors and a reference to the source for the colour (also B_T , V_T for bright stars?);
- the parallax with standard error (in mas);
- the proper motion components ($\mu_\alpha \cos \delta$, μ_δ) with errors (in mas/yr);
- flags to other parts of the catalogue: radial velocity, variable stars, double/multiple stars and remarks.

The machine-readable form should additionally give the complete correlation matrix of the five astrometric parameters.